

Feminist Thought of Rokeya: Re-Explication of her English Works

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Abstract

Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain was a pathfinder of the emancipation of Muslim women in Bengal. She was born in east-Bengal (present Bangladesh), but she lived in west Bengal or some time in another states of India for the sake of her husband's job. For educating Bengali women Sakhawat Memorial Girl's School has been set up by her. This institution has brought a drastic positive change in the history of female education in Bengal. On the other hand, Rokeya wrote on a number of social problems against the terrified condition of Muslim women. She imagined a 'Ladyland' through literary work Sultana's Dream, where women are free from all sorts of social prejudice and male domination. She showed here if women get chance to prove their intellectual faculties, they can do everything even scientific exploration. She brought up her feminist thought in Sultana's Dream. Basically, Rokeya criticized tartly to the patriarchal society of Bengal. As a result, she faced a lot of social obstacles, but she never stopped. This noble woman got the title as a 'Mother of Feminism' of Bengal. It should be noted, this article deals with Sultana's Dream, God Gives, Man Robs and Education Ideals for the Modern Indian Girl's. Sultana's Dream is the most focused area here. Therefore, this paper has been composed on the basis of two particular research questions, 1. How does Rokeya utilize the concept of a utopian society to critique androcentric society and advocate for women's advancement? 2. How does Rokeya's vision for a

gender-equal society where always men deprived the women in various ways? These questions explore several facts like feminist ideals, gender roles, patriarchy, women emancipation and empowerment, and overall conditions of Bengali society.

Keywords: Feminist, Novella, Trailblazer, Emancipation, Ladyland, Zenana

Introduction

Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain (1932-1880) is admired as a person and for her pioneering role in the emancipation of Muslim Women. She was a legendary Bengali writer and activist whose leadership had transformed the lives of thousands of people in this sub-continent. Rokeya in her writing represents the material and social condition of women's lives in colonial Muslim Bengal. She authored a great number of poetry, essays, articles, social-critical essays, books, short pieces and so on. She has written about women regularly in her contemporaries periodicals. By her writings she tried to motivate women to receive education and to remove social superstitions from their mind. Among her literary works Sultana's Dream is the most prominent creation. It's a feminist science fiction where she set up a Ladyland and this female country is ruled by women. In this novella she has shown the power of women. Simultaneously, In case women get free from the dominating phenomenon of patriarchal society, they can put their efficiency in every type of jobs like men or more better. Rokeya's feminist thought are clearly visible in Sultana's Dream. However, this article has been prepared mostly focused on Sultana's Dream. Moreover, A few scholars have been discussed regarding Rokeya's life and her different types of write up and the activities of the organization (Anjuman-e-Khawatine Islam) to the awakening of women in Bengal. But particularly there is no research article of her English works.

Aims and Objectives

- To analyze the nature of gender discrimination in the early twentieth century of the patriarchal society of Bengal.

- To achieve knowledge about the status and attitude towards the Bengali women.
- To raise awareness about the social and legal rights of women.
- To explore the power of women.

Literature Review

A number of esteemed scholars are discussed regarding Rokeya Shakhawat Hossain's works. For instance, Begum Rokeya: Somoy o Sahitya (Dhaka, 1982) by Morshed Shafiul Hasan, Begum Rokeya (Dhaka, 1983) by Abdul Mannan Sayeed, Rokeya Shakhawat Hossain: Jibon o Sahityakarma (Dhaka, 1986) by Muhammad Shamsul Alam, Bengali Women (Chicago, 1975) by Manisha Roy, Begum Rokeya: The Emancipator (Dhaka, 1980) by Safiuddin Joarder and Hasina Joarder, Reluctant Debutante: Response of Bengali Women to Modernization 1849-1905 (Rajshahi, Bangladesh, 1983) by Ghulam Murshid, Women's Changing Position in Bangladesh Tribute to Begum Rokeya (Dhaka, 2014) by Anwar Dil and Afia Dil, Women of Bengal (London, 1925) by M.M. Urquhat, Protesting Patriarchy Contextualizing Rokeya (Dhaka, 2006) By Nazma Chowdhury (Edited) and so on. These books are the significant source regarding Rokeya's life and works. But, there is no scholars particularly analyze Rokeya's novella Sultana's Dream as well as other English Works in one research work. Hence, this is the research gap here.

Research Methodology

This research has been done based on Rokeya's English work Sultana's Dream. Qualitative data and information must be extracted from different sources. Sultana's Dream authored by Rokeya is the main primary source. The article has been prepared with the assistance of secondary data also. The secondary data is collected from the different books, research articles, journals, lectures, newspapers and so on. Finally, analytical and descriptive methods have been followed to prepare this paper.

Birth and Family

Rokeya was born in 1880, to an aristocratic and conservative Bengali Muslim family in the village of Pairaband, Rangpur district under Bengal Presidency or mostly known as undivided Bengal. Her father Zahiruddin Muhammad Abu Ali Haider Saber was a Zaminder (fallen landlord) and a multi-lingual intellectual. Her mother Rahatunnesa Sabera Chaudhurani was a blind supporters of purdah¹ for women. Actually, Rokeya's family was not free from the conservative, narrow and obsolete ideas prevalent among the Muslims of that time. Rokeya remarked-

I had to observe purdah even for women from the age of five. I did not understand why it was improper to meet somebody, but I had to observe purdah...as soon as any women of the locality would come, somebody of our house would give a signal with the eye and I would run post-haste and hide myself anywhere... If I failed to understand the signal of the eye and came across somebody, the well-wishing elders used to say, 'How shameless the girl have become' (Joarder, 2014: 28).

In Rokeya's family gender discrimination were clearly visible and education was classified for male and female members. On the one hand, no education was given to her elder sister Karimunnesa Khanam Chaudhurani as well as younger sister Humaira Khanam Chaudhurani. Only they were taught to "read the Qur'an like a parrot without understanding the meaning". The learning of Bengali, English and any other languages was regarded as 'moral sin' (Shahanara, 2014: 88). On the other hand, Zahiruddin Muhammad Abu Ali Saber has sent his two sons whose names were Abul Asad Ibrahim Saber and Khalil Saber to St. Xaviar's college, Calcutta (Kolkata) to get modern education. Both the brothers secured best formal education in the contemporary era. Karimunnesa and Rokeya wanted to study Bengali against their family's wish. Ibrahim Saber secretly taught English and Bengali to Karimunnesa and Rokeya. After some time Karimunnesa married at the age of fourteen and later became a renowned poet (Shahanara, 1979: 63-69). Besides, Rokeya has a great determination to educate herself at any cost. She prevailed upon her brother Abul Asad Ibrahim Saber to teach her. Indeed, when

everyone has gone to sleep in their home at the night time, they would start studying together (Joarder, 2014: 29). After years when she became a distinguished writer, she dedicated her famous novel Padmarag to her brother Ibrahim Saber and saying, "... it was he who guided her and taught her to become what she did" (Tahmina, 1992: 39). Here mentionable that Rokeya dedicated her Sultana's Dream and Motichur to her elder sister Karimunnesa.

In 1897 Rokeya married at the age of eighteen with Sayed Sakhawat Hossain who was a widower. Sakhawat Hossain was serving as a deputy magistrate and he came from Bhagalpur of Behar (Murshid, 1993: 181). This Urdu-speaking person was educated in England. He has better knowledge in English and Bengali also. Apart from this, He was progressive and rational as well as liberal who saw Rokeya's potentialities in literary career. He assisted her to educate herself and become a good writer. With this encouragement and help within a short time Rokeya became proficient in English. They both are discussed at their free time about the deprivation of Bengali women (Rashed, 2016: 41). During her husband's lifetime Rokeya's literary output published in Indian periodicals that brought her into the limelight as a powerful writer. After that she began to know as Mrs. R. S. Hossain. Rokeya acknowledges her husband's positive contributions to her writing career, "If my dear husband had not been so supportive, I may never have written or published anything" (Murshid, 1993: 178). But there was not much happiness of her personal life. Two daughters were born to her but they both died too earlier. On the other hand, Sakhawat Hossain was about 26 years older than Rokeya. Most of the time her husband suffered from some chronic diseases and finally he died unexpectedly in 1909. After husband's death her step-daughter has made mental trauma. Moreover, Rokeya's secluded life was full of depression. In spite of all obstacles she engaged and devoted to herself as an emancipator of contemporary Muslim Women.

Educational Contribution

Rokeya's husband Sakhawat Hossain had left about 10,000 taka before his 44 death. With this money Rokeya established a Girl's School on 1 October in 1909 at Bhagalpur. But the irony of fate is that she could not stay long time here. She had to leave for Calcutta (at present Kolkata)

in 1910 and in the next year re-opened her school, the Sakhawat Memorial Girl's School, at waliulla Lane in a small class room. Initially, Rokeya got only eight girls to teach in her school (Sonia, 1996: 156). It was so difficult to collect more students due to the social prejudice in Bengali society. Most of the people had conservative, they were not ready to send their daughters to get education in the institution. In these circumstances, Rokeya went from door to door for collecting female students in Muslim families. Gradually she has got a few numbers of girls for her newly established Institution. According to a statistical report, there were 39 students in 1913 in Sakhawat Memorial Girl's School (Sonia, 1996: 157). Due to increase students day by day the school shifted at 13, European asylum Lane. Besides, the institution became an upper-primary school in 1915 and that time Sakhawat Memorial Girl's School moved at 86/A, Layer Circular road due to increase the number of students (Shymoli and Others,1998: 134). After years, students have been increased and the school became a middle-English school in 1917. Another point is that, every year she added a class till it became a high school in 1931 (Sonia, 1996: 159). Rokeya strongly believed, "The future of India lies in its girls". So, she emphasized on the importance of education for the girls that will in the long run intellectual and moral development of them.

Literary Activities

The literary career of Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain started from the very beginning of twentieth century. Her husband always supported to write about the condition of Bengali women. She has written Pipasha ('Thirst') that was her first literary work. She authored the books Motichur-1 (1904), Motichur-2 (1922), Padmarag (1924) and Abarodhbasini (1931). Her English works Sultana's Dream (1908) and two essays- "God Gives, Man Robs" (1927) and "Educational Ideals for the Indian Girls" (1931) which were published in the contemporary magazine The Mussalman. Her last work and unfinished essay was "Narir Odhikar". Apart from her all literary works, Delicia Hatya (Bengali translation of The Murder of Delicia by Marie Corelli) was remarkable. Rokeya has a great deal of essays, satire, short stories, poetry, letter and so on. Her few works could not come to the light widely.

Sultana's Dream : A Paradise of Feminism

Rokeya was a tireless fighter who wished to change the overall condition of Bengali Muslim Women. Among her all prominent works, Sultana's Dream was more dominant. It's a feminist utopia which one of her best English-language writing. At the very first time, Sultana's Dream was printed in well-known periodical the Indian Ladies Magazine in Madras, India in July 1905 (Anisuzzaman, 1969: 98). Actually, Rokeya wrote this piece of work when she lived in alone, because her husband went outside from home for official purposes. Rokeya's imaginary power was so high. It has been taken only two days to write this utopia. Rokeya mentioned, "When Sakhawat came back after two days and he asked casually, what she did in his absence. Then Rokeya showed him the story, Sakhawat Hossain read the whole writing silently and when he finished, he startlingly said, "A Terrible Revenge" (Rokeya Rachanaboli, Abdul Kadir Edited, 1989: 252). Even, he was so delighted to see Rokeya's literary intensity as well as English skill.

For the English lingual correction, Shakhawat Hossain instantly sent the piece of novella to the commissioner Mr. Jhon Macpherson (1745-1821) who was a British administrator in Bhagalpur of that period. But surprisingly, it did not require. Mr. Macpherson returned the writing along with a testimonial to Rokeya that stated-

"The ideas expressed in it are quite delightful and full of originality and they are written in English... I wonder if she has foretold here the manner in which we may be able to move about in the air at some future time. Her suggestions on this point are most ingenious" (Shahanara, 2014: 80).

In Sultana's Dream Rokeya visualized by her imaginative faculty in a 'Ladyland' where women rule over men. For the reason that women of her society lived in degrading situation and they did not get opportunity like men for self-development. In that case, she depicts a female country (Ladyland) where women are superior in mental faculties and sensible as well as to enjoy full freedom (Mafidul, 2009: 12). In Sultana's Dream, the name of the first character or the heroin of this novella 'Sultana' who is dreaming. It's better to say that Rokeya expressed herself

as ‘Sultana’. Sultana met a woman in dream whom she considered to her friend ‘Sara’. And later on, there are find another character that is ‘The Queen’. In the starting point of Sultana’s Dream, Rokeya remarked-

“One evening I was lounging in an easy chair in my bed- room and thinking lazily of the condition of Indian womanhood. I am not sure whether I dozed off or not. But as far as I remember, I was wide awake. I saw the moonlit sky sparkling with thousands of diamond-like stars, very distinctly (Rokeya, Sultana’s Dream, Rokeya Rachanaboli: 477).

Actually, Sultana and Sara were visiting Lady Land together. In the keen description of Ladyland are visible in the first stage of the Sultana’s Dream. In dream while walking Sultana with Sara, she found that, ‘the town was fully awake and the streets alive with bustling crowds. I was feeling very shy, thinking I was walking in the street in board daylight, but there was not a single men visible’ (Rokeya: 478). When Sultana felt that passers-by who were all women and they made jokes at her. She asked Sara, “What do they say”? Sara replied, “The women say that you look very mannish”. And Sara explained the meaning of the word mannish- “They mean that you are shy and timid like men”(Rokeya:479). As a matter of fact, Sultana was not accustomed to walking unveiling. Sara assured her, “You need not be afraid of coming across a man here. This is Ladyland, free from sin and harm. Virtue herself reigns here”. Sara mean that wherever women are free from all kinds of male dominance, there is no fear and suffering of them (Hasna, 2014: 37). Besides, this type of state is totally crime free.

While walking in Ladyland Sultana was enjoying the mesmerizing scenery of it. Then she did find a great deal of women but not a single man. She asked to Sara- “Where are the men?”. Sara replied- “In their proper places, where they ought to be”(Rokeya, Sultana’s Dream, 1908: 8). Sultana was astonished to hear that. She could not realize, what did convey Sara. She wanted to know about the proper places of men. Sara explained, “O, I see my mistake, you cannot know our custom, as you were never here before. We shut our men indoors” (Rokeya, 1908: 10). Instantly Sultana said “Just we are kept in the Zenana?”. Sara replied, ‘exactly so’. She smiled to

hear that. Actually, Ladyland is a place where women are totally free from male domination. Sultana agrees regarding the men customs of the society which women kept in seclusion or Zenana.² In fact, in Bengali society generally women were secluded. Simultaneously, they believed that women are inferior to men. It might be God created women as weaker. For that reason, Sultana was astonished. Conversation between Sultana and Sara-

“It is not safe for us to come out of the Zenana, as we are naturally weak.

Yes, it is not safe so long as there are men about the streets nor it is so when a wild animal enters a market place...

Suppose some lunatics escape them and put them back into their asylum and begin to do all sorts of mischief to men, horses and other creatures, in that case what will your countrymen do?

They will try to capture them and put them back into their asylum.

Thank you! And you do not think it wise to keep sane people inside an asylum and let loose the insane? ...

As a matter of fact, in your country this very thing is done! Men, who do or at least are capable of doing no end of mischief, are let loose and the innocent women shut up in the Zenana! How can you trust those untrained men out of doors?” (Rokeya, 1908: 14).

Here Sara compared to the men with the furious animals. She meant that since men are not trustworthy, women should not believe them. But Sultana again described the power of Indian men. She revealed, “We have no hand or voice in the management of our social affairs. In India man is lord and master. He has taken to himself all powers and privileges and shut up the women in the Zenana” (Rokeya, Rokeya Rachanaboli, 1973: 479).

In above mentioned dialogue expressed the helplessness of Bengali women in their patriarchal society even in family. Sultana discusses the most dominating power of Indian male

people who always uplift their superiority in the society. At the same time, they consciously treat themselves as a lord and master which is the most superior authority of their respected family and society. They enjoy all supreme power and privileges as opposed to secluded women from their legal rights.

Sara wanted to know, why Indian women allow themselves to be shut up. Sultana replied- Because, they are not stronger than men. In response Sara said, “A lion is stronger than a man, but it does not enable him to dominate the human race. You have neglected the duty you owe to yourselves and you have lost your natural rights by shutting your eyes to your own interests...they are fit for nothing” (Rokeya, 1908: 16). Sara neglectfully told about Indian men- they are not fit for anything. So, they should be kept into the Zenana.

As soon as Sultana reached Sara’s bungalow she was surprised. The house was neat and well-furnished which around a heart-shaped garden. Sara asked to Sultana, whether she knows knitting and needle work. Sultana replied that definitely, because they have not anything to do else in Zenana (Shamsul, 1989: 116). In Ladyland officers and researchers are done their duties very swiftly. Whereas the Indian magistrates, Judges, subordinate judges and other officers wasted their time by smoking or gossiping during the office time. Here is the crystal-clear difference of the working efficiency between women and men. If women get opportunity they can show more proficiency rather than men.

Sultana and Sara talked about different issues of the Ladyland. By the discussion Sultana came to know, there is no epidemic disease yet they did not suffer from mosquito bites. It is very surprising to Sultana that Sara’s kitchen was so clean and bright because she used solar heat to cook food instead of coal and fire. On the other hand, Indian people did not know about the solar energy till day (Tahmina, 1992: 72). Sultana wished to know how they learned the use of solar heat. In circumstances, Sara explained a brief history of Ladyland. The Queen who was the ruler of Ladyland, circulated an order that all women in her country must be educated. She founded a number of girl’s school these are financed by government. Gradually education spread among the women. Besides, early marriage was stopped. The Queen established few universities, where

only women were studying. She encouraged the women to engage scientific research (Hasna,2014: 45). Indeed, the women of Ladyland was so powerful and intelligent also. Sara mentioned, “Women’s brains are somewhat quicker than men’s” (Rokeya, 1908: 73).

Sara mentioned the superiority of women among all creations in this globe. In this way, there are a lot of dialogues in Sultana’s Dream which exposed Rokeya’s feminist thought. Interesting thing is that the men of Ladyland never come out from the chain. Finally, they were remained in ‘Mardana’ (opposite word of Zenana) (Rokeya, 1908: 74).

Moreover, it must be remarked that Sultana’s Dream is an arcadia. In this novella, Rokeya dreamed a Ladyland. This is the female region as well as noble area. Since the Ladyland ruled by female and male people are captive into the house, so women enjoying all social and legal rights. They developed their mental abilities and efficiency along with education and various types of scientific explorations. Rokeya’s imagination was not wrong. After ages later, that came true (Murshid, 1993:184). She has translated her Sultana’s Dream into Bengali language which name is ‘Sultana’r Swapna’ in 1922 so that the Bengali women who do not know English can easily go through this writing. To be noted in context that, Sakhawat Hossain believed in the emancipation of Bengali women. During his study time in England, he has got an opportunity to know closely about the English women who were more dynamic and educated (Maleka, 2011: 269). After returning home he encouraged his wife Rokeya to do something for the betterment of Bengali women. Rokeya has got huge assistance from her husband to change the situation of the women of Muslim society in Bengal. However, Rokeya’s short fiction Sultana’s Dream created a drastic reaction among the people of that time. It was a great challenge to all the traditional ideas of the contemporary Bengal (Shahanara, 2014: 85).

Rokeya’s another English work was “God Gives, Man Robs”. This essay was published in the contemporary magazine The Mussalman on December 6 in 1927. In this article she wanted to find fault with the men. Reason is that God means Almighty Allah has given all rights of women, Alternatively Men deprived the women from their all legal and social rights. The last English work of Rokeya was “Education Ideals for the Modern Indian Girl’s”. In this essay she

inveighed against the education system of India. Aside from these, Rokeya has written a number of English letters regarding her school and so on. She also established Anjuman-e-Khawatine Islam in 1916, a Muslim Women's Association to protect women from degradation and to enhance the various facilities of them (Maleka, 1989: 68). It is worth mentioning that Rokeya's thought regarding women emancipation in Bengal before the ages of Shikha Movement or Buddhir Mukti Andolon (Shibnarayan, 1977: 10-15). One of the famous reformers of Shikha Movement named Abul Hossain commented on Sultana's Dream. He told that this novella strengthen the power of women (Mafidul, 2009: 13). Moreover, Rokeya Shakhawat Hossain was a trailblazer of women emancipation in Bengal. She established a Girl's school for the institutional education of the female students. She tried hard to take care of the underprivileged women under the organization of Anjumane Khawatine Islam. Globally renowned novelist E.M Foster compared to Rokeya with Vergina Wolf. He remarked that they both are the esteemed thinker regarding the emancipation of women in their respective society (Foster, 1943: 21).

Conclusion

Rokeya Sakhawat Hossain was the trailblazer of female education in the Muslim society in undivided Bengal. She was a woman far more advanced and progressive than her contemporaries. She grapples with the problems of gender and identity against a cultural backdrop of generated expectations of women in Muslim patriarchal society. She declared the solution regarding that. She tried to make a hassle free, right and smooth path for the women who were neglected and dominated by their male members of the family from decades. To this end, she wrote about the betterment of women in her society, whenever got time. One of her best composition is Sultana's Dream and that magnificent work is the heaven of feminism. Moreover, in the history of world's literature Sultana's Dream is a master piece. Rokeya believes in feminism as well as humanitarian secularism. She is the light-house in terms of awakening and ensuring the emancipation of women in Bengal.

Notes

1. According to Encyclopaedia Britannica - Purdah, also spelled Pardah, Hindi Parda (Screen or Veil), practice that was inaugurated by Muslims and later adopted by various Hindus, especially in India and that involves the seclusion of women from public observation by means of concealing clothing (include the veil) and by the use of high walled enclosures, screen and curtains within the home.
2. The term 'Zenana' means, the part of a house reserved for the women and girls of a household in Muslim and Hindu families in the Indian Sub-continent.

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